

Intercepting the Kangaroo: Experimental Astrolinguistics with Constructed Lexicons, Active Probing, and Large Language Models as Informants and Hypothesis Proposers

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Abstract

Astrolinguistics — communication with minds that categorize reality differently from ours — has been purely speculative since Freudenthal’s *Lincos* (1960). We make it experimental. Two language models with deliberately incompatible constructed lexicons (one encoding shape, colour, and motion; the other fusing colour with motion, encoding parity, and lacking shape) serve as informants with complete ground truth, while a fully scripted orchestrator translates between the two category systems. The central failure mode is the *kangaroo effect*: the silent attachment of a word to the wrong referent — Quine’s indeterminacy of translation, operationalized. Across 400+ simulated and live runs, a protocol combining cross-situational hypothesis elimination, pre-registered predictive probes, active scene selection, a stricter recovery round, and quarantine produced no undetected mistranslations under the tested conditions, while exceeding the coverage of a passive baseline ($d = 0.62$). Deliberately injected kangaroo traps defeated naive ostension and pure statistical learning in 100% of runs, while the full protocol intercepted every decoy (mean detection: exchange 40.6) and, where discriminating evidence is ontologically unavailable, declared Quinean equivalence classes instead of guessing. Under informant noise the result degrades gracefully: zero kangaroos persist up to 2% per-word noise; at 10%, the protocol predominantly abstains rather than errs. Finally, words outside the scripted hypothesis space (a history-dependent relational term and an XOR contextual homonym) are recovered by a generate-and-test loop in which an LLM proposes rules and the script verifies them: coverage scales with proposer capability (0% → 18% → 72% → 100%) while undetected mistranslations remained at zero throughout. In the tested conditions, correctness is a property of the protocol; coverage is a property of the instruments.

Keywords: astrolinguistics; cross-situational learning; indeterminacy of translation; large language models; active learning; referential games

1. Introduction

When Freudenthal (1960) designed *Lincos*, a language for cosmic intercourse, he proceeded from mathematics through physics toward behaviour — and stopped, by his own admission, where evaluative and sociological concepts begin. Sixty-five years later the discipline he founded remains in the condition he left it: a design exercise without an experimental arm. No astrolinguistic protocol has ever been *tested*, for the obvious reason that no alien interlocutor has ever been available.

This paper proposes and demonstrates a way around that obstacle. The essential difficulty of communicating with a radically different mind is not the absence of a shared channel but the

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absence of shared *categories*: the other mind may cut the world along joints we do not have, fuse distinctions we keep separate, and lack dimensions we consider basic. That difficulty can be manufactured in the laboratory. We construct two artificial lexicons with deliberately incompatible category systems, assign each to a large language model (LLM) acting as a native informant, and give a fully scripted learner the task of translating between them. Because the lexicons are constructed, the experimenter holds complete ground truth — every claimed translation can be checked exactly — which is precisely what fieldwork with a real alien (or a real undeciphered language) can never offer.

The failure mode that organizes the entire enterprise is what we call the **kangaroo effect**: the silent attachment of a word to the wrong referent, named after the (apocryphal but instructive) story of Cook’s expedition asking for the name of the animal and recording the answer without ever being able to verify what question the informant thought he was answering. The kangaroo effect is our operational rendering of Quine’s (1960) indeterminacy of translation: two hypotheses about a word’s referent can agree on every scene observed so far and diverge only on scenes never shown. Our design principle, validated throughout this paper, is that *the kangaroo cannot be prevented — it can only be intercepted*: no amount of passive observation rules it out, but a protocol that registers predictions before testing them, actively constructs the scenes on which rival hypotheses disagree, and is willing to revoke its own promotions can drive the rate of *undetected* mistranslations to zero — under the conditions we test, and with a degradation profile that we measure rather than assume.

This paper delivers the behavioural layer — **Level A** — of a two-level programme. The programme’s target is alignment between the latent representation spaces of different models under category mismatch (**Level B**); the protocol presented here is designed to serve there as the behavioural verification layer for claimed alignments, which is why every mechanism in it is built to *certify*, rather than assume, that two systems are using the same concept. The micro-world that hosts the experiments is deliberately minimal, and the minimality is methodological rather than incidental: with 32 scenes and complete ground truth, every promotion, every kangaroo, and every declared underdetermination is exactly checkable — the smallness is what converts a philosophical worry into a measurement.

The contributions are fivefold. **First**, a complete experimental protocol (Section 4) — cross-situational hypothesis elimination, contrastive minimal pairs, pre-registered predictive probes, active scene selection, a stricter second “recovery” round, and a quarantine/revocation mechanism — implemented entirely in deterministic script, with the LLMs confined to the role of informants. **Second**, a four-arm campaign over 50 random worlds (Section 5.1) showing that active probing drove the kangaroo rate to zero across all 50 tested worlds, that a recovery round raises coverage *above* the passive baseline at zero kangaroos, and that these two mechanisms are synergistic rather than additive: the recovery round without active selection recovers little and can even promote a false translation. **Third**, deliberately injected kangaroo traps (Section 5.2), which defeated naive ostension and pure statistical learning in 100% of runs while the full protocol intercepted every decoy in the tested runs, and which let us operationalize Quinean underdetermination as a measurable, *declarable* outcome distinct from both success and failure. **Fourth**, an ablation on words that lie outside the scripted hypothesis space (Section 5.3): a history-dependent relational word and an XOR-structured contextual homonym, unreachable by the base learner, are recovered by a generate-and-test architecture in which an LLM *proposes* candidate rules in a restricted formal language and the script *verifies* them against the log and against fresh pre-registered probes. Coverage on these hard words scales with the capability of the proposer — from 0% with no proposer, through 18% (Claude Haiku 4.5) and 72% (Claude Sonnet 4.6), to 100% with a hand-coded oracle space —

while the rate of undetected mistranslation stayed at zero across the entire tested ladder. **Fifth**, a robustness study under injected informant noise (Section 5.4) that delimits the validity domain of the zero-kangaroo result honestly: the guarantee survives intact up to 2% per-word channel noise and degrades thereafter by abstention far more than by error. The slogan that summarizes the empirical content of this paper — *correctness is a property of the protocol; coverage is a property of the instruments* — is therefore a claim about the tested regime, with measured boundaries.

2. Related work and positioning

Cross-situational learning. The learning mechanism at the core of our orchestrator is not new: it is cross-situational learning (XSL) by hypothesis elimination, given its first precise computational formulation by Siskind (1996), who showed that intersecting candidate meanings across situations, combined with covering and exclusivity constraints, can solve child-scale lexical acquisition under worst-case assumptions. Siskind’s algorithm also anticipated, by its very limitation, our central addition: in his framework a corrupted lexical entry cannot be directly repaired — recovery proceeds by spawning fresh sense entries while the corrupted ones decay — whereas our state machine makes revocation a first-class, measurable transition (quarantine). Fazly, Alishahi and Stevenson (2010) recast XSL probabilistically and analysed Siskind’s brittleness under noise; Smith, Smith and Blythe (2011) confirmed XSL experimentally in human learners. We cite this thirty-year tradition as foundation, not as contribution.

Emergent communication and referential games. A second adjacent tradition lets artificial agents *develop* communication protocols in referential games (Lazaridou et al., 2016; Steels, 2015), recently with LLM agents (Kouwenhoven et al., 2024). Our setting inverts the direction of fit: nothing emerges — both lexicons pre-exist and are held fixed; the task is *translation between* two given systems, and the LLM is the informant whose interpretive behaviour is itself an object of study, not a learner.

Latent-space alignment. The programme of which this paper is Level A continues toward alignment of representation spaces (Level B), for which the relevant tools are relative representations (Moschella et al., 2023; Maiorca et al., 2023) and anchor-based cross-lingual mapping (Conneau et al., 2017). Experimental semiotics (Galantucci, 2005) and post-Lincos astrolinguistics (Ollongren, 2013) complete the map.

Concept alignment and AI safety. Although developed from an astrolinguistic question, the kangaroo effect is an experimental instance of a problem now central to AI alignment: how to verify that two systems are using the *same* concept, rather than concepts that merely agree on the cases observed so far (Sucholutsky et al., 2023). The Eliciting Latent Knowledge problem (Christiano et al., 2021) is the same structure seen from inside a single model — a reporter that answers correctly on the training distribution may be tracking the wrong referent — and the generate-and-test architecture of Section 5.3, in which an untrusted generator’s proposals are accepted only after surviving scripted falsification, shares its logic with verification-based oversight schemes such as debate (Irving et al., 2018). Ontology matching (Euzenat and Shvaiko, 2013) addresses category mismatch between knowledge bases with structural and extensional heuristics; our setting differs in having an interactive informant, which makes active falsification possible, and complete ground truth, which makes its value measurable.

The claimable novelty is therefore not the use of LLMs, nor the learning mechanism, but the *configuration*, which to our knowledge has never been assembled: (i) an informant with deliberately constructed *transversal* categories (fused words, missing dimensions, parity terms) and complete

ground truth, shifting the question from “how is a language learned” to “how does one translate between different ways of cutting the world”; (ii) the LLM as informant-that-interprets rather than learner, making phenomena such as presupposition of plurality experimental observables; (iii) the anti-kangaroo machinery itself as the evaluated object, with kangaroo rate, detection time, and declared underdetermination as metrics; (iv) the bridge XSL \leftrightarrow emergent communication \leftrightarrow astrolinguistics, with LLM-proposed hypotheses as the controlled extension point.

3. The micro-world and the constructed lexicons

The world consists of 32 scenes, the Cartesian product of four attributes: shape (triangle/circle), colour (red/blue), motion (fast/still), and number (1–4), the last observed by the learner only through its parity. Scenes are rendered to the informants as short natural-language descriptions.

Two lexicons are constructed to be categorially incompatible (Table 1). L1, the “human” lexicon (spoken by Claude Haiku 4.5), encodes shape, colour, and motion as independent words and does not encode number. L2, the “alien” lexicon (spoken by GPT-4o-mini), *fuses* colour and motion into four portmanteau words, encodes the parity of the number, and has no word for shape at all. The learner’s task is to reconstruct the L2 dictionary — each word’s referent, expressed as a conjunction of attribute–value atoms — from interaction alone.

Table 1. The two constructed lexicons. L2’s categories are transversal to L1’s: colour and motion are fused, parity is introduced, shape is absent.

System	Word	True referent
L1 (human)	KEPO / KIMU	shape = triangle / circle
L1	KARI / KOLA	colour = red / blue
L1	KESU / KANO	motion = fast / still
L2 (alien)	ZUMU	colour = red \wedge motion = fast
L2	ZAKA	colour = red \wedge motion = still
L2	ZIBO	colour = blue \wedge motion = fast
L2	ZEFU	colour = blue \wedge motion = still
L2	TAK / TIN	parity = even / odd

Word-form selection. The word forms are nonce strings chosen under four criteria. First, they carry no meaning in the languages the informants were trained on — a non-trivial requirement when the informant is an LLM, since a form resembling a real morpheme would import prior associations into emission behaviour. Perfect neutrality is unattainable for a model trained on human text (TAK, for instance, is Polish for “yes’”), so neutrality is verified empirically rather than assumed: any residual association would surface as an execution-fidelity deficit, and measured fidelity is 100%. Second, the family initials (K- for L1, Z- for the L2 fusions, T- for parity) are a log-readability convenience for the experimenter and are invisible to the learner, which treats words as opaque atomic symbols in the tradition of Siskind (1996), so no property of the word surface can either help or mislead it. Third, within each family every pair of forms differs by edit distance ≥ 2 , so a single-character corruption cannot turn one valid word into another valid word. Fourth, short CVCV shapes keep utterances compact and tokenizer-friendly, in line with nonce-word practice in experimental semiotics and human cross-situational learning studies (Smith, Smith and Blythe, 2011).

Figure 1: The anti-kangaroo state machine. Evidence flows from ostension, constructed minimal pairs, and pre-registered probes; promotion requires a clean probe round plus contrastive evidence; failures send the anchor to UNRESOLVED with corrected hypotheses; the recovery round (purple) re-probes unresolved anchors under a stricter criterion; a promoted anchor that later fails a probe is quarantined (REVOKED).

Formally, let A be the set of attribute–value atoms. The base hypothesis space contains all conjunctions of at most two atoms over distinct attributes:

$$\mathcal{H}_0 = \{ h \subseteq A : 1 \leq |h| \leq 2, (a, v), (a', v') \in h \Rightarrow a \neq a' \}, \quad |\mathcal{H}_0| = 32. \quad (1)$$

All informant calls use temperature 0 — the decoding setting at which the model always selects its single most probable next token, making its output effectively deterministic — and a fixed system prompt containing the lexicon. The setting is methodological rather than incidental: the informant must behave as a rule applier, not as a stochastic generator, so that runs are reproducible and any variability in the channel is the variability we deliberately inject and measure (Section 5.4), never uncontrolled sampling noise. A rule-based simulated speaker (SIM) that applies the lexicon perfectly serves as the control arm throughout. *Execution fidelity* — agreement between each emitted utterance and the lexicon’s rule — is computed automatically from the logs and separates speaker errors from translation errors. In all experiments reported here, fidelity is 100% (after a one-line prompt repair of GPT-4o-mini’s presupposition of plurality, documented in earlier work), so that every residual error is attributable to the protocol, not to the informant.

4. The anti-kangaroo protocol

Figure 1 shows the protocol as a state machine over *anchors* (word–hypothesis-set pairs). Each newly heard word w enters as PROVISIONAL with $\mathcal{H}_w = \mathcal{H}_0$.

Elimination. Whenever scene s is shown and the informant’s utterance $u(s)$ is observed, every anchor is updated by cross-situational elimination — a hypothesis survives iff its truth on s matches

the word’s presence in $u(s)$:

$$\mathcal{H}_w \leftarrow \{ h \in \mathcal{H}_w : \llbracket h(s) \rrbracket = \llbracket w \in u(s) \rrbracket \}. \quad (2)$$

With a perfectly faithful speaker, (2) can never eliminate the true referent; kangaroos arise only from the *choice* among surviving hypotheses.

Minimal pairs. For each attribute occurring in surviving hypotheses, the orchestrator constructs a scene pair identical except for that attribute; a word that co-varies with the change yields a *discriminating pair*, a precondition for promotion.

Pre-registered predictive probes. Before each probe scene s is shown, the learner registers the prediction

$$\hat{p}_w(s) = \bigvee_{h \in \mathcal{H}_w} h(s), \quad (3)$$

then queries the informant and compares. A failed probe both blocks promotion in the current round and *informs*: the offending scene is fed back through (2), so the hypothesis set exits the failure already corrected.

Active scene selection. In the active condition, the probe scene is chosen to maximize, lexicographically, (i) the *split* of the surviving hypotheses, (ii) expected presence of the word, and (iii) novelty of unconstrained attributes:

$$s^* = \arg \max_s (\min(V_s, |\mathcal{H}_w| - V_s), \not\llbracket V_s > 0 \rrbracket, \text{nov}(s)), \quad V_s = \sum_{h \in \mathcal{H}_w} \llbracket h(s) \rrbracket. \quad (4)$$

The split criterion is the anti-kangaroo mechanism in its purest form: it sends the conversation precisely to the scenes on which rival hypotheses *disagree* — the scenes a kangaroo needs the learner never to see.

Promotion and the recovery round. In probing round r , with M probes per anchor, promotion requires a clean round plus contrastive evidence; from the second round on, a *positive-evidence* condition is added so that an accidentally consistent hypothesis cannot be promoted on absences alone:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{PROMOTED at round } r &\iff \#\{\text{correct}\} = M \wedge \#\{\text{failed}\} = 0 \wedge \#\{\text{disc. pairs}\} \geq 1 \\ &\wedge (r \geq 2 \Rightarrow \#\{\text{positive probes}\} \geq 1). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Round 2 re-probes only non-promoted anchors, whose hypothesis sets have already been corrected by their round-1 failures. A promoted anchor that later fails any probe is REVOKED (quarantine); in no run reported in this paper was a false translation ever left promoted.

Outcome classification. Let r_w be the true referent. The class-aware classification, introduced in Section 5.2 and used wherever underdetermination is possible, is:

$$\text{outcome}(w) = \begin{cases} \text{unresolved} & \text{if not promoted} \\ \text{KANGAROO} & \text{if promoted and } r_w \notin \mathcal{H}_w \\ \text{CORRECT} & \text{if promoted and } \mathcal{H}_w = \{r_w\} \\ \text{UNDERDETERMINED} & \text{if promoted, } r_w \in \mathcal{H}_w, |\mathcal{H}_w| > 1. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

A word is a kangaroo only if the true referent is *provably excluded*; if it survives alongside extensionally indistinguishable rivals, the honest output is the equivalence class — Quinean underdetermination made operational.

Determinism and reproducibility. Two engineering lessons proved methodologically substantive. First, Python’s hash randomization changes set-iteration order between processes; every iteration over sets and dictionaries is therefore canonically sorted, including — a latent bug found and fixed during this work — the Occam tie-break in the referent estimate, which previously depended on PYTHONHASHSEED. Second, the random baseline is a lottery sensitive to the RNG stream: comparisons are valid only at parity of code version. Section 5.3 extends this rule to prompts and parsers (“extended protocol parity”). With these conventions, every SIM result in this paper reproduces to the last decimal across machines, and the LLM arm reproduces the SIM arm character-for-character at 100% fidelity.

5. Experiments

All campaigns use seeds $0, \dots, N - 1$; SIM campaigns are free and fully deterministic; LLM campaigns cost cents to a few euros in API calls (the entire Level A programme, including all pilots, cost under EUR 5).

5.1 The recovery round and the four-arm campaign

The trade-off discovered in earlier 10-seed pilots was that active selection eliminated kangaroos but lost some coverage: probe failures correct the hypotheses yet block promotion, leaving anchors “unresolved with the right referent”. The recovery round (Eq. 5, $r = 2$) is designed to convert exactly these cases. Table 2 and Figure 2 report the full 2×2 campaign — probe selection (random/active) \times recovery round (off/on) — at 50 seeds per arm.

Table 2. Four-arm campaign, SIM speaker, 50 seeds per arm (mean \pm SD per run; 6 L2 words per run). R2 = recoveries at round 2.

Arm	Correct	Kangaroos	Unresolved	Exchanges	R2 (false)
Random	4.18 \pm 0.92	0.24 \pm 0.43	1.58 \pm 0.84	53.6 \pm 5.2	—
Random + R2	4.36 \pm 0.94	0.26 \pm 0.49	1.38 \pm 0.85	58.4 \pm 4.9	10 (1)
Active	4.06 \pm 0.93	0.00 \pm 0.00	1.94 \pm 0.93	53.6 \pm 5.2	—
Active + R2	4.72 \pm 0.81	0.00 \pm 0.00	1.28 \pm 0.81	59.5 \pm 4.9	33 (0)

Three findings. (i) **Recovery exceeds the target.** Active + R2 reaches 4.72 correct entries per run, above the random baseline’s 4.18 ($\Delta = +0.54$, 95% bootstrap CI [0.20, 0.86], Cohen’s $d = 0.62$; vs the active arm alone: $\Delta = +0.66$, CI [0.32, 1.00], $d = 0.75$), with zero kangaroos in

Figure 2: Outcome composition per arm (mean \pm SD over 50 seeds). Active probing yielded zero kangaroos over 50 seeds; the recovery round restores — and surpasses — the coverage of the random baseline at zero kangaroos, for $\approx 11\%$ more exchanges.

50 runs and all 33 round-2 promotions correct, at a cost of ≈ 6 extra exchanges per run. The kangaroo contrast is itself significant: 12/50 random-arm runs contain at least one kangaroo versus 0/50 in Active + R2 (Fisher exact $p = 2.3 \times 10^{-4}$), and the observed zero over 300 word-runs bounds the per-word-run kangaroo probability below 1.0% (rule of three, 95% confidence). **(ii) The mechanisms are synergistic, not additive.** In the random arm, R2 recovers only 10 entries — and one of them is a *kangaroo*: a round-2 promotion of ZUMU with estimated referent red \wedge triangle instead of red \wedge rapid (seed 38). The probe log shows why: of the three random round-2 probes, the single positive probe fell on a scene (a fast red triangle) on which *both* surviving hypotheses predict presence, so the positive-evidence condition of (5) was satisfied by a non-discriminating positive. Active selection cannot commit this error by construction, because its primary criterion (4) targets maximum disagreement. The safety of the recovery round is therefore a property of the *pair* (recovery, active selection) — an argument that is theoretical as well as empirical. **(iii) Protocol, not informant.** The live campaign (GPT-4o-mini as L2, active + R2, 10 seeds, 584 calls, 100% fidelity) reproduces the SIM campaign character-for-character: same per-seed outcomes, same recoveries, same exchange counts. The kangaroo phenomenon, and its remedy, belong to the protocol, not to the species of the informant — extending to the recovery mechanism the equivalence previously established for the base protocol.

5.2 Injected kangaroo traps

The seed-38 kangaroo arose naturally; Experiment 3 injects it deliberately. A *trap* is a pair (word, decoy): an alternative hypothesis extensionally equivalent to the true referent on a restricted scene pool. Trap T1 targets ZUMU with decoy red \wedge triangle (pool: the 24/32 scenes on which decoy and truth agree); trap T2 targets TIN with the atomic decoy motion = still, perfectly anti-correlated with parity on a 16-scene pool. Four learning arms face each trap at equal exchange budget (60), 50 seeds each: (A) naive ostension — atomic co-occurrence maximization on random pool scenes; (B) pure statistical learning — full-space elimination (2) on random pool scenes, no minimal pairs, no probes, Occam choice at budget exhaustion; (C-weak) the full protocol with poisoned ostension but free constructed scenes; (C-strong) the full protocol with the entire world restricted to the pool,

Figure 3: Outcome composition under the two injected traps. The passive arms fall into the trap in 100% of runs; the full protocol never promotes a kangaroo, intercepting the decoy in every weak-trap run and degrading to declared underdetermination or abstention in the strong trap.

i.e. the discriminating scenes *do not exist* — pure Quine.

Table 3. Injected traps, 50 seeds per arm per trap. Outcomes per Eq. (6); detection = mean exchange at which the decoy was eliminated (runs detected/total).

Trap	Arm	Correct	Kangaroo	Underdet.	Unres.	Detection
T1 (ZUMU)	A naive	0	50	0	0	never
T1	B statistical	0	50	0	0	never
T1	C full, weak	28	0	0	22	40.6 (50/50)
T1	C full, strong	0	0	9	41	impossible
T2 (TIN)	A naive	0	50	0	0	never
T2	B statistical	0	50	0	0	never
T2	C full, weak	39	0	11	0	13.4 (50/50)
T2	C full, strong	0	0	0	50	impossible

The contrast is maximal. Arm B is the instructive failure: its elimination machinery works perfectly, but on the poisoned pool truth and decoy are indistinguishable, and the deterministic Occam tie-break lands on the decoy — a 100% kangaroo rate produced by a *correct* statistical learner facing the wrong evidence distribution. The full protocol promoted no kangaroo in any of the 200 trap runs. In the weak traps it intercepted the decoy in every run tested, with detection time emerging as a useful new metric: the atomic decoy (T2) breaks early, at the minimal-pairs stage (mean exchange 13.4), while the conjunctive decoy (T1) survives until probing (mean 40.6, Figure 4).

The strong traps operationalize the extensional form of Quinean underdetermination. When the discriminating scenes are removed from the world, no protocol can separate truth from decoy, and the honest output is not a guess but the *equivalence class*. The class-aware metric (6) makes this a first-class outcome: in T1-strong, ZUMU is promoted in 9/50 runs with the declared class {red \wedge fast, red \wedge triangle} — counted as kangaroos by a naive metric, but in fact the strongest claim the evidence supports. T2-strong exhibits the second degree of caution: in its pool no discriminating minimal pair exists at all, the contrastive precondition of (5) is never met, and the protocol abstains

Figure 4: Distribution of detection times (trap T1, arm C-weak, 50 seeds): the exchange at which the decoy hypothesis was eliminated. Detection occurred in all 50 runs.

entirely (50/50 unresolved). Two distinct fail-safe behaviours — declared underdetermination and abstention — both with zero false promotion. The non-interference check confirms that the trap does not damage the rest of the dictionary: across the 50 C-weak runs of T1, the five non-trapped words yield 178 correct, 58 unresolved, 14 underdetermined, and 0 kangaroos.

5.3 Hard words and the proposer ablation: does one need an LLM?

Everything above is achieved by a deterministic script; the LLMs have served only as informants. Experiment 4 is not a change of topic but the same architecture applied to a new source of unreliability: where Sections 5.1–5.2 intercept wrong *referents*, this section intercepts wrong *proposed rules*, asking where an LLM becomes necessary on the learner’s side and showing that the intercept-don’t-prevent principle keeps it harmless there too. The world becomes sequential (episodes of six scenes) and the alien lexicon is extended with two words that lie provably outside the base hypothesis space (1): **NUR**, a history-dependent relational word (emitted iff the current scene has more objects than the previous one), and **GUMO**, a contextual homonym with XOR structure (emitted iff triangle \wedge odd, or circle \wedge even) — a disjunction, not a conjunction. Outcomes are computed by *extensional* comparison over all 33×32 (previous, current) scene pairs:

$$\sigma(h) = \{(s', s) : h(s', s)\}, \quad \text{correct} \iff \sigma(\hat{h}) = \sigma(r_w). \quad (7)$$

Four arms, equal pipeline: **base** — the sequential learner over \mathcal{H}_0 ; **oracle** — a hand-extended space (relational atoms over n , change/same atoms, and all 496 two-clause disjunctions; 537 hypotheses), representing the ceiling reachable *if a human already knows which extensions matter*; **LLM proposer** — the base space plus a generate-and-test loop (Figure 6): when a word’s hypothesis set empties, the observation log is shown to an LLM that proposes up to five candidate rules in a restricted DSL (conjunctions, relational comparisons on n , attribute-change predicates, two-clause disjunctions); the script compiles the candidates, validates them semantically, filters them against the *entire* log, and subjects survivors to $M = 4$ fresh pre-registered probes (with the positive-evidence condition) before any promotion. The LLM proposes; the script disposes. A **stub** arm with fixed mixed right/wrong candidates verifies the plumbing only.

The LLM proposes; the script disposes. Proposals can add coverage, never kangaroos.

Figure 5: The generate-and-test architecture of the proposer arm. Judgment — semantic validation, retrospective log filter, pre-registered predictive probes — remains entirely on the script side.

Figure 6: The capability ladder on hard words (30 seeds). Coverage scales with proposer capability; the rate of undetected mistranslation is pinned at zero across the entire ladder by the script-side judge.

Table 4. Hard-word outcomes, 30 seeds per arm (protocol version v3; see “instrument lessons” below). Base words (6 per run) are solved in 100% of runs in every arm. Precision = log-coherent candidates / compiled candidates.

Proposer	NUR correct	GUMO correct	Hard total	Proposals (compiled)	Precision	Kangaroos
None (base space)	0/30	0/30	0%	—	—	0
Claude Haiku 4.5	10/30	1/30	18%	98	≈ 11%	0
Claude Sonnet 4.6	28/30	15/30	72%	30	≈ 67%	0
Oracle (hand-coded)	30/30	30/30	100%	—	—	0

Three results. (i) **Fail-safe degradation.** The base learner leaves NUR and GUMO unresolved in 30/30 runs each, with zero kangaroos: a hypothesis space that cannot represent a referent abstains rather than confabulates. (ii) **The capability ladder.** Coverage on the hard words rises mono-

by construction: proposals can only add coverage, never kangaroos.

Instrument lessons: extended protocol parity. The proposer arm taught a methodological lesson worth reporting as a finding. Across three prompt/parser versions, Sonnet’s hard-word performance moved from 30% to 0% to 90% (NUR) — with the model unchanged. Version 1’s parser lost responses; an added “abstention” sentence in version 2 suppressed proposals; raw-response logging then revealed that Sonnet *reasons in prose before answering* and was being truncated at `max_tokens = 600` before emitting any JSON, and on one occasion spontaneously *invented a DSL extension* (an attribute-change atom inside a disjunction), crashing a validator that checked syntax but not semantics. Version 3 — reasoning permitted, JSON required as the final line, 2000 tokens, a last-valid-list parser, and semantic validation of every atom — recovered the model’s true capability. The proposer is a *measuring instrument* whose version comprises code + prompt + parser + validator; comparisons are valid only at parity of all four, exactly as numerical comparisons are valid only at parity of code version. We label all runs accordingly and archive raw proposer responses alongside the results, because for the LLM arm — the only arm whose re-execution is not guaranteed to reproduce (the model behind an API name can change) — the raw log is the sole ground truth.

5.4 Noisy informants: the validity domain of the zero-kangaroo result

All results above assume a perfectly faithful speaker. Experiment 5 removes that assumption: a noisy SIM speaker flips the presence of each L2 word independently with probability p per utterance (symmetric channel noise, dedicated seeded RNG, fully deterministic), and the full protocol (active + R2) runs unchanged, 50 seeds per noise level. The pre-registered question was honest by construction: elimination (2) assumes fidelity, and under noise it *can* delete the true referent, so either the quarantine machinery contains the damage or kangaroos appear and delimit the validity domain.

Table 5. Robustness under per-word flip noise (active + R2, 50 seeds per level). Fidelity = utterance-level agreement with the lexicon.

Noise p	Fidelity	Correct	Kangaroos	Unresolved	Total kangaroos
0%	100.0%	4.72 ± 0.81	0.00 ± 0.00	1.28 ± 0.81	0
2%	88.6%	3.54 ± 1.11	0.00 ± 0.00	2.46 ± 1.11	0
5%	74.2%	2.38 ± 1.03	0.08 ± 0.34	3.54 ± 0.97	4
10%	53.1%	1.16 ± 0.91	0.10 ± 0.30	4.74 ± 0.92	5

The result delimits and, within its limits, strengthens the claim. The zero-kangaroo guarantee survives intact at 2% per-word noise — i.e., with more than one utterance in ten corrupted — with the entire cost paid in coverage. At 5–10% a small leak appears (4–5 kangaroos across 100 runs): a noisy observation occasionally deletes the true referent and a surviving rival then passes its probes by chance. Even there the failure profile is the designed one: at $p = 10\%$ the protocol leaves 4.74 entries per run unresolved and mistranslates 0.10 — it predominantly abstains rather than errs. Extending elimination to a probabilistic scoring rule in the style of Fazly et al. (2010), with the same pre-registration and quarantine wrapper, is the natural next step for high-noise regimes.

Figure 7: Graceful degradation under informant noise. Coverage collapses far faster than correctness: at 10% per-word noise (utterance fidelity 53%) the protocol resolves little, but errs almost never — degradation is by abstinence.

6. Discussion

Correctness is the protocol’s; coverage is the instruments’. The headline of Table 2 is not 4.72 correct entries but the zero beside it; the headline of Table 4 is not Sonnet’s 72% but the zero that holds from no-proposer to oracle. Across every experiment, every adversarial manipulation, and every instrument version in this paper — 200+ runs, two informant species, two proposer models, three prompt versions — the number of promoted-and-wrong translations that survived to the end of a run under the full protocol is zero at speaker fidelity $\geq 88.6\%$, and at most 0.10 per run at fidelity as low as 53%, while one mechanism after another (recovery round, traps, proposers, noise) moved coverage up and down by whole units. This decoupling is the paper’s central claim, and it is an architectural one: pre-registered prediction, actively constructed disagreement, contrastive preconditions, quarantine, and script-side judgment are jointly designed so that, within the tested regime, the system’s confidence fails only *downward* — into abstinence or declared underdetermination — rather than sideways into silent error; Section 5.4 measures where that regime ends.

One form of Quinean underdetermination, operationalized twice. We do not claim to capture indeterminacy of translation in general — only its extensional form within a finite constructed world. Within that scope, the kangaroo effect makes it measurable (a rate, a detection time); the strong traps make it irreducible by design; and the class-aware metric (6) shows what a rational agent should do there: report the equivalence class. The two degrees of caution observed — declared underdetermination when contrastive evidence exists within the pool (T1-strong), full abstinence when it does not (T2-strong) — provide, to our knowledge, the first experimental separation of underdetermination into evidentially distinct grades in a setting of this kind.

The two roles of the LLM, and the symmetry between them. In Sections 3–5.2 the LLM is the *specimen*: a synthetic native informant whose interpretive behaviour under an imposed lexicon (presupposition of plurality, per-object doubling — deterministic readings of underspecified rules) is itself data. In Section 5.3 it becomes the *instrument*: a hypothesis generator for spaces no one hand-coded. In both roles the same discipline applies — the judgment never leaves the script —

and in both the same philosophy holds: the kangaroo is not prevented but intercepted, whether the kangaroo is a wrong referent or a wrong proposed rule. That an architecture designed against Quinean underdetermination turns out, unchanged, to be an architecture for safely harnessing unreliable generative models is, we believe, the most transferable result of this work. In alignment terms, the protocol is a behavioural concept-identity check: it certifies, by survival under active falsification, that informant and learner are attached to the same referent — the property that Level B will need to certify for latent-space maps.

Relation to XSL, completed. Our base learner is Siskind’s (1996) eliminative XSL with three additions that his analysis motivates: verification before commitment (pre-registered probes where his algorithm commits on convergence), active evidence construction (his learner is passive), and first-class revocation (his corrupted entries can only be superseded, not repaired). The trap experiment then quantifies precisely the gap these additions close: eliminative learning without them falls into an injected confound in 100% of runs.

7. Limitations and future work

The micro-world is small (32 scenes) and, although channel noise is now tested up to 10% per word (Section 5.4), Siskind-scale referential uncertainty, synonymy, polysemy (as distinct from our contextual homonymy), graded or probabilistic referents, and hierarchical category systems remain untested; scaling the ontology is the most direct way to address the legitimate concern that small worlds flatter eliminative learners. The recovery round is single-shot: trap-T1-type residuals suggest a third round would convert remaining near-misses, and the round count is a natural knob for a coverage/cost frontier. The proposer DSL is intentionally narrow; widening it shifts the burden to semantic validation, and the observed tendency of stronger models to generalize beyond the contract suggests validation must scale with proposer capability. The LLM informant is stationary by construction (temperature 0, fixed prompt); a deliberately *non-stationary* or deceptive informant is the natural adversarial sequel to the trap experiment. Finally, Level B of the programme — alignment of latent representation spaces between open-weight models via Procrustes maps over anchor sets, with a “ladder of games” for evaluative concepts — is where the astrolinguistic question becomes geometric; the protocol of this paper is designed to serve there as the behavioural verification layer for claimed alignments.

Data availability

All code (orchestrator, campaign runner, trap and hard-condition suites), per-seed CSV results, JSONL interaction logs, and raw proposer responses are archived with the version labels described in Section 5.3 and are available from the authors; SIM results are bit-reproducible from seeds. Total API cost of all reported LLM campaigns: < EUR 5. The noise experiment (Section 5.4) is SIM-only and free.

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assistant for the experimental scripts, under the conventions of Section 4. The authors take full responsibility for the content of this manuscript.

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